

Diversity of 7 SL RNA from the signal recognition particle of maize endosperm

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ABSTRACT

An 11 S ribonucleoprotein particle was isolated from maize endosperm and shown to be functionally and structurally equivalent to the mammalian signal recognition particle. However, unlike animal cells which apparently contain a single 7 SL RNA species, maize endosperm contains a heterogeneous population of 7 SL RNA. To investigate this diversity, we have cloned and sequenced a number of the maize endosperm 7 SL RNAs isolated from functionally active SRP preparations. Some maize 7 SL RNAs are strikingly similar, differing by single base changes or short deletions; surprisingly, others share less than 70 percent sequence homology. Despite differences in primary sequence, nearly identical secondary structures can be suggested for all maize 7 SL RNAs, consistent with a proposed functional role in protein translocation for each of these RNAs. The amount of new available sequence data enabled us to define two conserved regions of presumed functional importance: A conserved sequence -G-N-A-R- in the center of a variable region which forms a well defined stem-loop and possibly is involved in an interaction with the 19 kDa protein of the SRP. Secondly, three short nucleotide stretches located in the central domain of 7 SL RNA may form part of a dynamic RNA-switch structure.

INTRODUCTION

The signal recognition particle (SRP) is required for the translocation of secretory proteins across the membrane of the endoplasmic reticulum (see 1, for review). The canine pancreas SRP is an 11 S ribonucleoprotein particle consisting of six different proteins and the 7 SL RNA (2,3). 7 SL RNAs characterized in *Drosophila* (4) and in *Xenopus* (5) have been shown to be also present in plants (6,7). In the process of protein translocation, the SRP interacts with the ribosome and the signal peptide of a nascent protein. The resulting complex is targeted to the membrane of the endoplasmic reticulum via the SRP-receptor (7-9). Both 7 SL RNA and SRP appear to possess an elongated two-domain structure (10,11). The larger of the two domains is composed of the central region of the 7 SL RNA and the 19 kDa, 54 kDa, 68 kDa and 72 kDa proteins; the smaller domain consists of the two terminal regions of the 7 SL RNA and the 9 kDa and 14 kDa proteins. It is believed that the latter domain

influences translation, while the larger domain is directly involved in protein translocation (12-14).

The high degree of evolutionary conservation of 7 SL RNA underscores the importance of the 7 SL RNA in the process of protein translocation. Secondary structures are very similar and maintained by compensatory base changes between different species (10). A variety of 7 SL RNAs can be used interchangeably in reconstitution experiments with isolated canine SRP proteins to give rise to functionally active particles (15). Within a given species the population of animal 7 SL RNAs found in SRP seems to be highly homogeneous resulting in one single band on denaturing polyacrylamide gels. In contrast, in plants, we find a heterogeneous population of 7 SL RNAs. We have cloned and sequenced maize endosperm 7 SL RNAs from functionally active 11 S SRPs. A variety of related, but distinctly different 7 SL RNAs is identified. The large number of new 7 SL RNA primary sequence data has allowed us to define conserved regions of likely functional importance, common to all SRPs.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

7 SL RNA isolation and polyadenylation

SRP was purified from maize endosperm as described previously (7). The RNA was extracted with phenol of which about 250 ng (2.8 pMol) were used in the polyadenylation reaction containing 250 μ Mol ATP, 500 mg/ml BSA (RNase-free, Boehringer) 11.6 units RNasin (BRL), 20 μ Ci 32 P- α ATP (3000 Ci/mMol, Amersham), 260 mM NaCl, 10 mM MgCl₂, 2.5 mM MnCl₂, 50 mM TrisHCl pH 8.0 and 0.25, 0.5, or 1 unit of E. coli polyA polymerase (BRL) in a reaction volume of 20 μ l. Incubation was for 20, 30 or 60 min in each case at 37 °C after which the reaction was terminated by the addition of EDTA pH 8.0 to a final concentration of 40 mM and put on ice. The RNA was separated from unincorporated nucleotides by passing it through a Sephadex G50 spun column which had been equilibrated with yeast tRNA. The RNA was recovered in the first two fractions. The sample was extracted twice with phenol and once with chloroform. 1/10 volume of 3 M Na-acetate was added and the sample was incubated over night at 0 °C. The RNA precipitate was pelleted for 45 min by centrifugation at 40,000 g using a Sorvall SS34 rotor.

cDNA synthesis and cloning

cDNA synthesis was performed by the method of Gubler and Hoffman (16) using oligo-dT as a primer, AMV reverse transcriptase, RNase H, E. coli DNA polymerase I and T4 DNA polymerase (all enzymes from Boehringer). Efficient synthesis of the first and the second strand was monitored independently using 32 P- α dCTP in the reactions and analysis of the DNA on alkaline 2% agarose gels (17). cDNA was extracted twice with

phenol and once with chloroform. 2 µg yeast tRNA was added as a carrier and the cDNA was precipitated by adding NH₄OAc₂ to a final concentration of 2 M and incubation at 0 °C overnight. cDNA was recovered by a 45 min centrifugation at 40,000 g in a Sorvall SS34 rotor. About 5 µg (5.2 pMol) of pBS M13+ DNA (Stratagene) was digested at the unique SmaI restriction site in 50 µl of 10 mM TrisHCl pH 7.5, 10 mM MgCl₂, 20 mM KCl and 16 mM DTT with 20 units of SmaI for 2 hrs. at 25 °C. 20 units of calf intestine alkaline phosphatase (Boehringer) were added and the sample was incubated for 1 hr at 37 °C. Dephosphorylation was terminated by the addition of EGTA pH 7.5 to a final concentration of 22 mM and an incubation at 65 °C for 10 min. Proteins were removed by the addition of 25 µl 7.5 M NH₄OAc₂, an incubation on ice for 20 min and a 10 min centrifugation. The supernatant was extracted once with phenol and once with chloroform and the DNA was precipitated at 0 °C for 1 hr after the addition of two volumes of ethanol. Ligation was performed using 25 ng of cut and dephosphorylated vector and 20 ng of cDNA, 100 µM ATP and 100 units of T4 DNA ligase (New England Biolabs) in 50 mM Tris HCl pH 7.6, 10 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM DTT. Incubation was for 2 hrs. at room temperature. Preparation of competent XL1-Blue (Stratagene) E. coli cells and transformation with the ligated DNA was executed according to Dagert and Ehrlich (18). Transformants were selected on LB agar plates containing 0.2 µg ampicillin per ml, 50 µl of 2% XGAL and 10 µl 100 mM IPTG per plate. Recombinants containing inserted cDNA were selected as colorless colonies and were plated on LB agar plates containing 12 µg/ml tetracycline to assure the presence of the complementing F'-plasmid. Clones containing cDNA inserts in the range of 300 bp or longer were selected after the preparation of plasmid DNA on a small scale and its digestion with the restriction enzymes PvuII, EcoRI, PstI or XbaI.

Sequencing

The sequence of inserted cDNA was determined using the dideoxy sequencing protocol of Sanger et al. (19). The 5'-terminus of the RNA was sequenced using a synthetic deoxyoligonucleotide (CCACCTTAATGCCCC) complementary to nucleotides near the 5'-end of the 7 SL RNA. The oligonucleotide was labeled at the 5'-end using ³²P-γATP and polynucleotide kinase; 18 pMol of oligonucleotide and 26 pMol of ATP were incubated in 50 mM TrisHCl pH 7.6, 10 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM DTT with five units of polynucleotide kinase (New England Biolabs) for 1 hr at 37 °C in a volume of 20 µl. The reaction was terminated by the addition of 200 mM EDTA pH 8.0 to a final concentration of 20 mM and transferring the sample onto ice. 10 µl yeast RNA (1 mg/ml) and 100 µl TE were added and the RNA was separated from unincorporated nucleotides by passing the sample through a Sephadex G25 spun column equilibrated in water. About 0.15 pMol of 7 SL RNA and 0.36 pMol of

oligonucleotides were annealed in 12 μ l buffer (50 mM Tris HCl pH 8.3, 60 mM NaCl, 10 mM DTT) by heating at 90 $^{\circ}$ C for 3 min and cooling down to 37 $^{\circ}$ C during a 45 min period after which the sample was put on ice. Reverse transcription was performed in 50 mM TrisHCl pH 8.3, 60 mM NaCl, 6 mM MgOAc and 10 mM DTT. dNTP concentrations of 400 μ M and ddNTP concentrations of 240 μ M were used. Incubation was at 37 $^{\circ}$ C for 30 min. The sequence was determined after separation of the DNAs on 12 % polyacrylamide gels (acrylamide/bisacrylamide 19:1) containing 7 M urea and 1X PB (20).

RESULTS

SRP-isolation

Maize endosperm SRP was isolated from seeds of inbred maize (W64A, *Zea mays* L.) 20 days after pollination essentially as described for the isolation of mammalian SRP (2). The homogenization and extraction of the maize SRP has been modified and described (7). SRP was obtained as 11 S fractions from sucrose gradients. These fractions were either phenol extracted for the analysis of the RNA or used in functional assays to test for the ability to translocate proteins across maize endosperm salt washed microsomal membranes.

RNA isolation from functionally active maize endosperm SRP

In Figure 1, the electrophoretic profile obtained after separation of phenol extracted RNA derived from the 11 S peak fractions of the sucrose gradient is shown. Several RNA species which differ slightly in their electrophoretic mobility can be distinguished in the SRP isolated from maize endosperm (lanes 2 and 3). In contrast, only one RNA species of canine 7 SL RNA is detectable (lane 1). All RNAs isolated from maize endosperm SRP are of a slightly reduced electrophoretic mobility compared to the canine 7 SL RNA. Also, 5 S RNA is present in minor amounts in the sucrose gradient purified maize endosperm SRP.

11 S fractions containing 7 SL RNA were tested for their activity in the translation and translocation of the maize storage protein zein across salt washed microsomal membranes from maize endosperm. Figure 2 shows that pre-zein (pz) is processed to zein (z) only in the presence of purified maize SRP (lane 4). The processed protein is protected from the digestion of externally added proteinase K, providing evidence that it has entered microsomal vesicles (lane 5). Human platelet derived growth factor, a cytoplasmic protein (h, in Figure 2), was translated simultaneously in all reactions and, as expected, is not translocated and completely digested by proteinase K.

cDNA cloning and sequencing

To determine the differences between the 7 SL RNAs isolated from sucrose gradient purified maize SRP, we cloned and sequenced the RNAs. Phenol extracted RNA was

Fig. 1 7 SL RNA isolation. Separation of 7 SL RNAs from a nuclear salt extract from dog pancreas (lane 1) and from a sucrose gradient purified salt extract from maize endosperm (lanes 2 and 3) on a 7 % polyacrylamide gel containing 7 M urea. Lane 2 contains 1/4 of the amount of RNA as shown in lane 3. The positions of 7 S RNA and of 5 S RNA are marked by the arrows.

polyadenylated using ATP and *E. coli* poly-A polymerase. Optimal polyadenylation conditions were obtained using three different incubation times and enzyme concentrations as described in "Material and Methods". The efficient synthesis of the first and the second strand was monitored by independently labeling each strand with ^{32}P - α dCTP in the reactions after separation of an aliquot of the DNAs on alkaline 2% agarose gels (not shown). *Xenopus* 5 S RNA was used as a control in the polyadenylation and cDNA synthesis reactions. cDNA was ligated into plasmid pBS+ DNA (Stratagene) which had been cut and dephosphorylated at the unique *Sma*I restriction site. Competent XL1-Blue (Stratagene) *E. coli* cells were transformed and transformants were selected on LB agar plates containing ampicillin, XGAL and IPTG. Single stranded DNA was obtained after the addition of helper phage and sequences were determined by dideoxy sequencing of the respective clones in which the oligonucleotide 5' GTAAAACGACGGCCAGT 3' was used as a primer (see Material and Methods).

Fig. 2 Sucrose gradient purified SRP from maize endosperm is active in the translation and translocation of zein. Peptides were labeled with ^{35}S -methionine during translation and separated on 15% polyacrylamide gels containing SDS. Pre-zein (pz) mRNA was derived from plasmid pDS-M1 (35) and transcribed and translated in vitro in a wheat germ system. Lane 1: maize SRP was present, but not salt-washed maize microsomes. Lane 2: salt-washed maize microsomes were present at a concentration of 0.5 A_{280}/ml , but not maize SRP. Lane 3: proteinase K was added after the reaction. Lane 4: translation in the presence of maize SRP and maize salt-washed microsomal membranes. Lane 5: same as in lane 4, except proteinase K was added after the reaction. Zein (z) is protected from the digestion by protease K. Human platelet derived growth factor (h) was translated simultaneously in all reactions. Details of the experimental procedure are described in (7).

5'-terminal sequence

The 5'-terminus of the 7 SL RNAs was sequenced using an endlabeled synthetic oligonucleotide (5' CCACCTTAATGCCCC 3') as a primer in reverse transcriptase reactions (see "Material and Methods"). This oligonucleotide is complementary to a region 36 bases away from the 5'-end of the maize 7 SL RNAs. When the mixture of maize endosperm 7 SL RNAs was analyzed, a sequence could be determined unambiguously (Figure 4). Therefore, the 5'-terminal sequences of the 7 SL RNA (NCCGAGCUCUGUAGCGAGAGCUUGUAACCCGAGCG...) must be common to most, if not all 7 SL RNAs from maize endosperm (Figure 3).

Sequence comparison

Surprisingly, many 7 SL RNAs were found which differed at the primary sequence level, but nevertheless were related to each other to various degrees. In Figure 4, eleven of the maize 7 SL RNA primary sequences are shown in an alignment with each other and with the human 7 SL RNA (4) at the bottom of each panel. The sequences of ten clones which contained large cDNA inserts as well as of one clone

Fig. 3 Determination of the sequence of the 5'-end of the 7 SL RNAs from maize endosperm. An oligonucleotide labeled radioactively at its 5'-end and complementary to a region 36 bases away from the 5'-end of the maize 7 SL RNAs was used in sequencing reactions with reverse transcriptase containing different dideoxyoligonucleotides T, C, G and A as marked. Lane -: no dideoxy-oligonucleotides added. Lane 0: no enzyme added. * marks the position of the free oligonucleotide. Products were separated on a 12 % polyacrylamide gel (acryl/bisacryl 19:1) containing 7 M urea. The deduced sequence is shown at the right of the Figure.

(zm44) which is shorter but otherwise identical to zm29, are shown. Zm10, being identical to zm5, was isolated independently. All clones which contained smaller inserts could be fitted to one of the sequences shown in Figure 5. Some 7 SL RNAs are very similar, differing by single base changes (zm10 and zm3) or single base

	1	11	21	31	41	51	61
zm10	<u>NCOGAGCUCU</u>	<u>GUAGCGAGAG</u>	<u>CUUCUUAACC</u>	<u>GAGCGGGGC</u>	AUUAAAGU-G	GUGCGGAUC	UUUGCGAUG
zm5
zm50
zm3
zm29
zm44
zm14C.....G.
zm7	U.A.G.
zm17U A.....	U.....GU	..CCU..C..
zm25	U.....G.	..G.UACC..
zm36	U.....	..G.CAAU..U
human	G...G..G.G	..G...C.U.	.C.....GU..	C.....UACUC	GGAGGCUGA.C.G	GAG. AUCGU
	71	81	91	101	111	121	131
zm10	CUUUC-UGGG	CCC-GGGCUC	G-CUAUGUGC	C-UUUGCCG	GCCUGCCCG	CCCAAGUUG-	GUAGUGGCUG
zm5
zm50
zm3
zm29
zm44
zm14U.....	..-U...A	..C.A	..U...AU..
zm7U.....	..-U...A	..AC	..U...AU..
zm17	A...-CU	G...U...CU	..-G.....	..AC	U.....U..
zm25	-G...UU	..U...UC	A.UGG	..-UU	U.....C.
zm36	GG.G..AU	G...U...G..	U.AGUGC.A	A.AACU.UG	A..AC..AUCG.U
human	UGAGUCCA..	AGUUUC.GG	UGUAG..C..	UA.GCC.AUC	..GG..U...C	A.U...C.	..GCA.CAA..-
	141	151	161	171	181	191	201
zm10	GCGGAGGCUU	UAGCGGAAGC	UUU-GGUC-U	CUCCAGACCU	GAAGUGGCG	GAAUGGCUG	AGGCUGGCUU
zm5
zm50
zm3
zm29
zm44
zm14	A...-...C	...A.....	..G.....	..G.....	AC..C.....A
zm7	..U..G...C	...A.....	..G.....	..G.....	..G..C.....A
zm17	..U...-C	GG...A.G	C.G...C..	..UU	..C.....	..C.....
zm25	UU...A..	GG...U.G	CC...G.U	..CUUG	AU.....	..C.....U..
zm36	U...U..C.	..G...A..	..-A	UC...ACA	A...-G	AC..U..
human	AU..U.A.C	CCCG...GCG	GGG..AC..A	..CAGGUG..	A.G.A..GGU	..CC.GCCC	..UC...-A
	211	221	231	241	251	261	271
zm10	CACAGAGCA	CGAUCACUCG	CCCCTUCCA	ACGGUGGGAG	GAUAACG-GG	CCGCGCACU	UCGAGGCCAA
zm5
zm50
zm3A.
zm29
zm44
zm14A.....A.A.U.....
zm7A..C..AA.U.....U..
zm17A..U.....G.A.
zm25AUU.A.....	..A.....GC	AU.G..U.GC
zm36	..U.....	..GU...-	..CA..	G.....A..	..U..A.	U.....AUG.	AUAG.....
human	A..G.....	GUCA-..AA.U	..UGCUG.	U.A..A.UG.C.	..UG...A.	AGCCA.UGC.
	281	291	301	311	number of nucleotides		
zm10	CUCAGGCCCA	GA-GCCUCA	CUAAGCAGAC	CACCAUCUUU	309		
zm5	309		
zm50	309		
zm3	309		
zm29	308		
zm44	* 306		
zm14	..A..A.....	..U...U	..U...A..	307*		
zm7A.....	..A.....	305		
zm17	..-..U..	U...A..	308*		
zm25	U.A...U..	..CUU.A.AC	UA.....U..	304*		
zm36	U	304*		
human	..CA...UG	UG..-AA..U	AGC.AGAC..	CGUC.....	300		

*) for explanation see text

Fig. 4 Sequence comparison. Primary sequences of 7 SL RNAs from maize endosperm. The eleven different 7 SL RNA sequences were derived by dideoxy sequencing of the respective clones and are aligned with each other and with the known sequence from human 7 SL RNA (bottom of each panel). Dots indicate nucleotides identical to the sequence of zm10 shown on top of each panel. A dash indicates that no nucleotide is present at this position. The underlined stretch of nucleotides at the 5'-end was derived by direct sequencing of the RNA using reverse transcriptase.

deletions (zm10 and 29). Others have a homology of less than 70 percent (e.g. zm10 and zm 36). The length of the RNAs varies slightly from 304 to 309 nucleotides and all are somewhat larger than the human counterpart. All maize 7 SL RNAs seem to possess the same sequence at the 5' end as determined by direct sequencing of the RNA population by reverse transcriptase (see above).

Highly conserved regions among the 7 SL RNAs of maize and human are located at the extreme 5'-end, around position 120, and region 180 to 260 (Figure 4). These regions correspond to areas conserved also between human, *Xenopus* and *Drosophila* 7 SL RNA species (10). The region around position 50 is an area where several nucleotides in the maize sequences are inserted (with the exception of zm 36) causing the slightly larger size of the maize 7 SL RNAs.

Structural features common to all 7 SL RNAs

All 7 SL RNAs of maize endosperm have the secondary structure features of their animal counterparts. Figure 5 shows the postulated secondary structures of zm10 and zm36 derived by the use of the compensatory base change approach (21). Identical structures with only minor differences can be suggested which include the base pair interactions which previously had been only weakly supported by compensatory base changes between the animal 7 SL RNAs (e.g., bases around position 180 with bases around position 220) . Several base pairings are now consolidated in all the RNAs isolated from signal recognition particles (Zwieb, manuscript submitted) by comparison with the many different maize 7 SL RNAs. In contrast, another weakly supported interaction of the extreme 5'-end with nucleotides around position 40 is not present in the maize RNAs.

Nucleotides located in the stem of domain I are highly variable in sequence (Figures 4 and 5). However, the formation of the stem itself is highly conserved in the maize 7 SL RNAs as well as in all animal counterparts. Comparison of several 7 SL RNA sequences reveals the conservation of a four nucleotide sequence (-G-N-A-R-) which is always found to be single-stranded at the tip of the stem of domain I (Figure 6).

Another conserved structure is found at the junction of the three helices of domain I, II and the central domain. Here, an RNA structure is present which has previously been shown to be involved in the formation of alternative conformers (22). Figure 7 describes that this RNA-switch structure is present in all the 7 SL maize endosperm RNAs we have analyzed, as well as in other known 7 SL RNAs (see Discussion below).

Other conserved regions may or may not reflect important SRP-functions, but rather requirements for transcriptional control. At least two box A-elements possibly required for transcription by polymerase III, can be identified in the 5'-half of all maize 7 SL RNAs (not shown).

Fig.6. The single-stranded tip of the stem loop of domain I is conserved. Loops of all maize endosperm 7 SL RNAs of zm10 to zm36 (top row) are compared with 7 SL RNAs of other species from the same region (bottom row). The consensus (bottom, right) shows the sequence -G-N-A-R-.

DISCUSSION

Primary structure analysis of active maize endosperm SRP preparations

In order to be able to isolate sufficient SRP, a crude homogenate of maize endosperm was salt extracted directly, which, after sucrose gradient purification, results in a maize endosperm preparation which still contain low amounts of 5 S RNA (see Figure 1) and is not pure on the protein level (data not shown). Nevertheless, cloning and sequencing of a number of the RNAs in the 7 S range clearly showed that most, if not all RNAs derived from the active SRP preparation are not contaminating RNAs or breakdown products of larger RNA species, but rather related to RNAs of the 7 SL type.

The electrophoretic profile obtained after separation of phenol extracted RNA derived from the 11 S peak fractions of the sucrose gradient, reveals several RNA species with slightly different mobilities. We attribute these differences mainly to the different sizes of the RNAs, but other factors, e.g. base composition or slightly different conformations even under the denaturing conditions of the electrophoresis cannot be excluded. An assignment of a particular band to a certain RNA species as identified by cloning and sequencing was not attempted, since it is possible that a particular subfraction of the RNAs is not polyadenylated efficiently and escapes cloning. This might be true in spite of the fact that apparently a unique sequence is present at the 5'-end, as indicated by direct sequencing.

In the course of the experiment we have also cloned and sequenced maize endosperm 5 S ribosomal RNA. This sequence is in complete agreement with the sequence obtained previously by direct sequencing of the RNA (23). Since we obtained the identical 5 S sequence several times, it is very unlikely that mistakes

Fig. 7. Possible switch-structures at the meeting point of the three stems from domains I, II and of the central domain of 7 SL RNAs from different species. Region s can either interact with s' or with s". Only the two border structures, but not the possible intermediate base pairing schemes (compare Figure 5) are shown here (see text). The nucleotide being closest to the 5'-end of the RNA is marked by >.

during cDNA production using reverse transcriptase and DNA polymerase have been introduced, which might have been responsible for minor differences between some maize 7 SL RNA sequences.

Under the conditions of the cDNA synthesis ten to thirty 5'-terminal nucleotides were lost (16). In order to determine the 5'-terminal sequences directly, a synthetic deoxyoligonucleotide (5' CCACCTTAATGCC 3') was labeled radioactively at its 5'-end with ³²P-γATP and polynucleotide kinase. It is complementary to a conserved region 36 bases away from the 5'-end of the maize 7 SL RNAs and was used as a primer in sequencing reactions with reverse transcriptase. Perfect complementarity exists between most maize 7 SL RNAs and the deoxyoligonucleotide primer; two

mismatches are present between the oligonucleotide and zm36. Probably, only two mismatches would not prevent the priming from RNAs of the latter type. We conclude that, despite the sequence variability found in the maize 7 SL RNAs in general, the 5'-ends are very similar if not identical. Clearly, differences in the 5'-terminal nucleotide sequence in some maize 7 SL RNAs of minor abundance would not be detectable by direct sequencing.

Secondary structures

All 7 SL RNAs of maize endosperm have the secondary structure features of the animal counterpart (see Figure 5, for two examples). In addition, the overall pattern of the distribution of variable and conserved regions found in animal 7 SL RNAs is also present in the maize counterpart. The conservation provides evidence that all the maize 7 SL RNAs we have isolated are involved in a function related to signal recognition particle. Some of the previously very weakly supported base pair interactions have now been confirmed or ruled out on the basis of the large number of available maize 7 SL RNA sequences.

As detected in the animal 7 SL RNAs, an extensive variation in primary sequence of nucleotides in the stem-loop of domain I is also found in the 7 SL RNAs from maize endosperm; nevertheless, a tight stem-loop is formed in all cases. A particular conservation is found at the tip of domain I. The consensus of this short sequence is -G-N-A-R- and was deduced by comparison of all known 7 SL RNAs (Figure 6). Since loops need not be conserved per se, we suggest that the tip of the stem loop of domain I is involved in an important specific interaction with RNA or protein. We favor the latter possibility since preliminary 3D models of the 7 SL RNA suggest to us that domain II, and a large portion of the central domain, as well as the 5'-domain are possibly involved in interactions with the translating ribosome (manuscript submitted); in contrast, domain I would point away from the ribosome. Therefore, the top of domain I might be able to interact e.g. with protein components in the membrane, or with one of the proteins of the SRP which is involved in protein translocation. The 72 kDa, 68 kDa or the 19 kDa protein are three good candidates for such an interactions, since the other three SRP proteins (54 kDa, 14 kDa and 9 kDa) are either associated with the 5'-domain or do not bind to RNA directly (14,24). It has been shown that the 19 kDa protein can protect the top of domain I from digestion of the RNA by α -sarcin (27). Therefore, the single-stranded nucleotides of the sequence -G-N-A-R-, identified here, might be directly involved in binding to the 19 kDa protein.

Recently, the structural similarity between E. coli 4.5 S RNA, a part of Bacillus subtilis scRNA and the domain II of all known 7 SL RNAs, including the ones described here, was noticed (28-30). At the moment the functional significance of this homology is not clear.

RNA switching

Alternative base pairing ("switching") has been proposed previously to be important for some of the functions of SRP (10,22). The switch, which is characterized by the interaction of region s with either region s' or s", can be also suggested in the different maize 7 SL RNAs (Figure 7). These basepairing schemes might represent only two of several intermediate possibilities, one of which might exist as shown in Figure 5. It should be noticed that such multiple secondary structures cannot be proposed for other three-way RNA junctions e.g. present in ribosomal RNAs. The inability to suggest a stable interaction between s' and s" further demonstrates that the existence of multiple structures is not a general property of three-way RNA junctions. This finding further supports the idea that maize endosperm 7 SL RNAs are indeed involved in SRP function. We hypothesize that coordinate base pair changes, perhaps in combination with "sliding" inside the switch-structure, cause a smooth major structural change at the junction of the three helices without the need for a large input of energy. Probably the three regions s, s' and s" are conserved because they must satisfy the criteria for building up at least two different dynamic structures (25). By simply comparing the number of base pairs involved in the two interactions, the s,s" pairing is somewhat favored in most 7 SL RNAs, including the one from *Halobacterium halobium* (26), but unusual base-base interactions are expected to take place inside the switch too. If non-Watson-Crick interactions play a major role, it will be difficult to prove the existence of the dynamic structures by the conventional phylogenetic approach which currently uses only the obvious base compensations. Conflicting results have been reported recently, concerning the existence of the switch in *Schizosaccharomyces pombe* (31-33). In our analysis of the *S. pombe* 7 SL RNA, the s,s" interaction is clearly favored on the basis of standard base pairing rules. At the moment we cannot exclude the possibility that the switch is not present in *S. pombe* and therefore might not be a general property of all 7 SL RNAs.

Varieties of 7 SL RNA

Although some 7 SL RNAs isolated from maize endosperm SRP are very similar, differing by single base changes or deletions only, others have a homology of less than 70 percent. In contrast, a much closer similarity is usually observed even between species; e.g. human and *Xenopus* 7 SL RNAs are homologous to about 90 percent (10). Whereas very small changes are not expected to alter the activity of the SRP, a similarity of less than 70 percent between some maize endosperm 7 SL RNA is expected to impose a profound effect on SRP activity, even if the same or similar secondary structure models can be attained. Otherwise we have to assume that there is not need for sequence conservation of the 7 SL RNAs in maize endosperm in particular. Such a notion would have to be extended at least to most, if not all

monocotyledons, since also in wheat germ a heterogeneous pattern of 7 SL RNAs, is found (Marshallsay et al., unpublished).

Production of 7 SL RNAs of impaired functionality during the very active period of the accumulation of storage proteins by the endosperm cells of maize could provide an explanation for the observed variability. In other systems silent genes for 7 SL RNA exist which are probably never expressed (e.g. 34). The maize endosperm might be able to activate some of these genes during protein secretion and storage, and might use every possible 7 SL RNA related RNA, even if some of them might possess a suboptimal activity. It could be argued, on the other hand, that in this critical phase of maize development a need for a variety of optimized SRPs might exist. It is possible that different SRPs are used in the translation and translocation of different proteins. Different SRPs might also reflect the presence of specialized translocation apparatuses in the membrane.

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